

Rogério Leone Buchaim^{1*} and Daniela Vieira Buchaim²

¹Department of Biological Sciences (Anatomy), Bauru School of Dentistry, University of São Paulo (USP), Bauru, SP, 17012901, Brazil

²Human Morphophysiology (Anatomy), University of Marília (UNIMAR), Marília, SP, 17525902, Brazil and Postdoc Bauru School of Dentistry, University of São Paulo (USP), Bauru, SP, 17012901, Brazil

Dates: Received: 04 January, 2017; Accepted: 11 January, 2017; Published: 12 January, 2017

***Corresponding author:** Rogério Leone Buchaim, Associated Professor, Department of Biological Sciences (Anatomy), Bauru School of Dentistry, University of São Paulo (USP), Al. Dr. Octávio Pineiro Brisola 9-75, Vila Nova Cidade Universitária, CEP 17012-901, Bauru, São Paulo, Brazil, Tel: +55 14 32358220; Fax: +55 14 3235-8390; E-mail: rogerio@fob.usp.br

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Short Communication

Translational medicine basically aims to facilitate the integration of basic research with clinical research, with the aim of transferring the applicability of its benefits to the population as a whole [1,2]. According to Lean et al., "It is a process that part of the evidence-based medicine towards sustainable solutions to community health problems" [3].

In addition, translational research generates an increase in the capacity for health research with an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approach, forming, training and integrating a new generation of researchers [4].

Among the translational researchers with a strong focus on clinical applicability, it highlights the tissue regeneration, especially in bone and/or nerve repair. The recovery of bone loss or nerve damage, particularly in the areas of Medicine and Dentistry, lead to a constant demand for biomaterials and/or techniques that facilitate and propitiate the formation and regeneration of new tissue [5].

The development of new biomaterials and the use of stem cell therapies for application in regenerative medicine involve several translational researches [6]. To provide the formation of a new bone, biomaterials must be resorbable over time, have biocompatibility and biofunctionality, generate no immunological response and economically accessible, being the primary objective of tissue bioengineering [7].

Regarding the clinical applicability of the researchers on

Short Communication

Translational Medicine in Tissue Regeneration

nerve repair, the correct reinnervation of the target organs is the main objective of the nerve repair, in order to obtain a directed axonal regeneration that provides functional sensory and motor recovery. The location, type of injury, time of surgery, type of repair to be used, correct alignment of the fascicles, surgical technique and morbidities to be presented in the postoperative period should be taken into account in order to predict the results of peripheral nerve repair [8].

Based on this context, a group of Brazilian researchers, led mainly by Benedito Barraviera and Rui Seabra Ferreira Júnior (Center for the Study of Venoms and Venomous Animals - CEVAP, São Paulo State University - UNESP, Botucatu, São Paulo) since the 1990s, have been studying the new heterologous fibrin sealant composed of a serine protease extracted from *Crotalus durissus terrificus* venom and a cryoprecipitate rich in fibrinogen extracted from the buffaloes *Bubalus bubalis* blood [9].

This new biopharmaceutical has enormous potential application in Medicine and Dentistry [10], which presents greater purity, lesser toxicity and greater adhesiveness [11-15]. From 2011 we have been developing a clinical trial research I/II applying in patients with chronic venous ulcers [16,17].

Many researchers are developing translational researchers aimed at innovative applicability's for new biological materials, as the heterologous fibrin sealant, providing a scaffold for stem cells, for the correction of bone defects and nerve damage [18,19]. There are already drugs, derivatives of peptides or proteins of venoms, which are approved. Some of these are in clinical trials and others in several stages of preclinical development [20]. We emphasize the fact that most of them are developed in the Northern Hemisphere, but this Brazilian initiative proves to be very promising.

In conclusion, by obtaining high quality results in the regenerative processes of the tissues, translational researches favor the accessibility and rapidity in the recovery of human health, contributing in the improvement of the quality and life expectancy of the world population.

References

- Azevedo VF (2009) Translational medicine: what's the importance to rheumatologic practice? *Rev Bras Reumatol* 49: 81-83. [Link: https://goo.gl/1ZgbCi](https://goo.gl/1ZgbCi)
- Ferreira AS, Barraviera B, Barraviera SR, Abbade LP, Caramori CA, et al. (2013) A success in Toxinology translational research in Brazil: bridging the gap. *Toxicon* 69: 50-54. [Link: https://goo.gl/53dmhc](https://goo.gl/53dmhc)
- Lean MEJ, Mann JI, Hoek JA, Elliot RM, Schofield G (2008) Translational Research: from evidence-based medicine to sustainable solutions for public health problems. *BMJ* 337:a863. [Link: https://goo.gl/CIJ037](https://goo.gl/CIJ037)
- Ciesielski TH, Aldrich MC, Marsit CJ, Hiatt RA, Williams SM (2016) Transdisciplinary approaches enhance the production of translational knowledge. *Transl Res* S19315244(16)30353-X. [Link: https://goo.gl/mHI6jh](https://goo.gl/mHI6jh)
- Brahatheswaran D, Yasuhiko Y, Toru M, Kumar DS (2011) Polymer Scaffolds in Tissue Engineering Application: A Review. *Int J Polym Sci Article ID* 290602: 19. [Link: https://goo.gl/ua0PJ7](https://goo.gl/ua0PJ7)
- Richardson SM, Kalamegam G, Pushparaj PN, Matta C, Memic A, et al. (2016) Mesenchymal stem cells in regenerative medicine: Focus on articular cartilage and intervertebral disc regeneration. *Methods* 99: 69-80. [Link: https://goo.gl/GuALZH](https://goo.gl/GuALZH)
- Bhat S, Kumar A (2013) Biomaterials and bioengineering tomorrow's healthcare. *Biomatter* 3: e24717. [Link: https://goo.gl/ToRk8d](https://goo.gl/ToRk8d)
- Martínez de Albornoz P, Delgado PJ, Forriol F, Maffulli N (2011) Non-surgical therapies for peripheral nerve injury. *Br Med Bull* 100: 73-100. [Link: https://goo.gl/6PouvJ](https://goo.gl/6PouvJ)
- Ferreira Jr RS, Barros LC, Abbade LPF, Barraviera SRCS, Silveiras MRC, et al. (2017) Heterologous fibrin sealant derived from snake venom: from bench to the bedside - an overview. *J Venom Anim toxins incl Trop Dis*, [Epub ahead of print].
- Barros LC, Ferreira RS Jr, Barraviera SR, Stolf HO, Thomazini-Santos IA, et al. (2009) A new fibrin sealant from *Crotalus durissus terrificus* venom: applications in medicine. *J Toxicol Environ Health B Crit Rev* 12: 553-571. [Link: https://goo.gl/NJFgAw](https://goo.gl/NJFgAw)
- Perussi Biscola N, Politti Cartarozzi L, Ferreira Junior RS, Barraviera B, Leite Rodrigues de Oliveira A (2016) Long-Standing Motor and Sensory Recovery following Acute Fibrin Sealant Based Neonatal Sciatic Nerve Repair. *Neural Plast* 2016: 9028126. [Link: https://goo.gl/OWqzBt](https://goo.gl/OWqzBt)
- Vidigal de Castro M, Barbizan R, Seabra Ferreira R Jr, Barraviera B, Leite Rodrigues de Oliveira A (2016) Direct Spinal Ventral Root Repair following Avulsion: Effectiveness of a New Heterologous Fibrin Sealant on Motoneuron Survival and Regeneration. *Neural Plast* 2016: 2932784. [Link: https://goo.gl/RVCZqd](https://goo.gl/RVCZqd)
- Buchaim RL, Andreo JC, Barraviera B, Ferreira Junior RS, Buchaim DV, et al. (2015) Effect of low-level laser therapy (LLLT) on peripheral nerve regeneration using fibrin glue derived from snake venom. *Injury* 46: 655-660. [Link: https://goo.gl/7U6NaL](https://goo.gl/7U6NaL)
- Benitez SU, Barbizan R, Spejo AB, Ferreira RS Jr, Barraviera B, et al. (2014) Synaptic plasticity and sensory-motor improvement following fibrin sealant dorsal root reimplantation and mononuclear cell therapy. *Front Neuroanat* 8: 96. [Link: https://goo.gl/4Y0fku](https://goo.gl/4Y0fku)
- Barbizan R, Castro MV, Barraviera B, Ferreira RS Jr, Oliveira AL (2014) Influence of delivery method on neuroprotection by bone marrow mononuclear cell therapy following ventral root reimplantation with fibrin sealant. *PLoS One* 9: e105712. [Link: https://goo.gl/Ac9reU](https://goo.gl/Ac9reU)
- Abbade L, Barraviera SRCS, Silveiras MR, Ferreira Junior RS, Carneiro MTR, et al. (2015) A new fibrin sealant derived from snake venom candidate to treat chronic venous ulcers. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 72: AB271. [Link: https://goo.gl/kD4y00](https://goo.gl/kD4y00)
- Gatti MAN, Vieira LM, Barraviera B, Barraviera SRCS (2011) Treatment of venous ulcers with fibrin sealant derived from snake venom. *J Venom Anim Toxins incl Trop Dis* 17: 226-229. [Link: https://goo.gl/lclx6z](https://goo.gl/lclx6z)
- Oliveira Gonçalves JB, Buchaim DV, Souza Bueno CR, Pomini KT, Barraviera B, et al. (2016) Effects of low-level laser therapy on autogenous bone graft stabilized with a new heterologous fibrin sealant. *J Photochem Photobiol B* 162: 663-668. [Link: https://goo.gl/qIERuw](https://goo.gl/qIERuw)
- Buchaim DV, Rodrigues Ade C, Buchaim RL, Barraviera B, Junior RS, et al. (2016) The new heterologous fibrin sealant in combination with low-level laser therapy (LLLT) in the repair of the buccal branch of the facial nerve. *Lasers Med Sci* 31: 965-972. [Link: https://goo.gl/a4C1J9](https://goo.gl/a4C1J9)
- King G (2015) Venoms to Drugs: Venom as a Source for the Development of Human Therapeutics. Royal Society of Chemistry; London, UK. [Link: https://goo.gl/THN97V](https://goo.gl/THN97V)